

The use of social media platforms to improve teaching and learning for Chinese students

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ABSTRACT

Social media is gaining popularity among people not only for the purpose of interacting but also as a means of education and learning. Conventional methods of learning have been taking over by modern methods of learning using technological advancements. One among those advancements is the use of social media for teaching and learning for students scattered geographically. Social media platform is a combination of numerous communication channels like Facebook, Twitter, Skype, Blog Posts, YouTube, Wikipedia etc. Social media is a growing medium for advanced studies despite the fact that it is also a way for diverting students from studies. It helps in bridging the gap in communication and studies have shown that it is becoming a growing method of education and learning. This paper has been focused on the use of social media as a method of teaching and learning for the students specifically within the context of Chinese students.

Keywords: *Social media, learning, teaching, Chinese students.*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

Social media has been widely used for interaction purposes but now it has been changing its face and transforming into more useful form for teaching and learning purposes. Bogdanov, Limpens, Li, Helou, Salzmann, Gillet, asserted that previously, universities were it using among students for

education [3], however, Li and Chen, mentioned that it is now used for students of a host country and home country [8]. The international scope which social media has enabled Chinese students to use it for education. Social media allows Chinese student to use Renren and NetEase widely in China [1]. Contrastingly, UK students use Facebook and YouTube [7]. No matter which digital medium is used, the results show that it is aiding Chinese students in higher education.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The objective of this report is to investigate the use of different social media websites for teaching and learning. The report will begin with identifying the significance of social media and the type of medium used in higher frequency by people around the globe. Then the study will move towards the scope of social media in education. Finally, the focus will be given to the use of social media in the education of Chinese students and hindrances in the conventional method of teaching which compel students to use social media only. On the basis of the above-mentioned study, the analysis would be given about the usefulness of social media in education.

1.3 Thesis Statement

The use of social media platforms aid in improving teaching and learning for Chinese students.

1.4 Research Questions

- What are the available methods of educating students?

- Why is the scope of Social media platforms increasing in higher studies?
- How can the means of education and learning be improved?
- How can the use of Social media aid in teaching and learning of Chinese students?

2. METHODOLOGY

The method adopted for this research work is the use of qualitative techniques designed for research purpose. Data has been collected through archival research, interviews, and observation [4]. Archival research has been gathered from peer-reviewed articles which are used to complete this study. Twelve participants were interviewed during the survey from the students of four PRC's (Peoples Republic of China) universities to collect information on the subject of the scope of social media in education and observations were taken by emphasising Chinese students and noting their behavioural patterns. Moreover, additional data has been collected from an online survey that was also carried out by the researcher to aid the research about the knowledge of social networking websites by the students.

3. DISCUSSION

3.1 Available Methods for Education

Teaching is not just a profession, in fact, it is a technique which is exercised by the skilled people to make one able to develop his calibre and personality [7]. Teaching not only aims to improve the knowledge base of the students but it also shapes the strategies for effective and interactive teaching and motivating students [6]. There are primarily two methods of teaching; conventional and modern [3]. The conventional method is based on classroom teaching while modern method includes virtual studies and social media website [1].

3.2 Teacher-Centred Approach

As Pea, Nass, Meheula, Rance, Kumar, Bamford, Nass, Simha, Stillerman, Yang and Zhou highlighted, teachers are the sole authority in this approach [10]. They guide students through interactive learning session and lectures. The feedback from students is judged by taking assessments and exams [4]. According to Guy, teacher centred approach is better

because it provides one-to-one discussion and students mentioned that they find it easy to ask anything they want [6]. Similarly, according to Li and Chen, teachers said that they find it useful to get immediate responses from students [8]. However, the opponent of teacher-centred approach said that this approach handicapped a student's creative thinking ability [14]. Students are assumed as direct receptors only and teachers always abide by already prescribed rules and traditional methods [12]. There is no concept of creative learning and think. However, thinking out of the box means seeing things from a different perspective which would not be possible if a student has no creative ability [7].

3.3 Student-Centred Approach

Although the teacher is the authority in this approach, however, Duggan and Brenner stated that it is a two-way communication and interaction process in which teacher and students participate on equal footings. The teacher is no more than a facilitator [6]. The teacher does not teach everything to students as it is followed in teacher-centred approach rather, they are encouraged to share their opinion and contribute to the discussion [4]. This approach aims to enhance reliance of student on himself and encourages creative learning by giving group projects, assignment, role plays, class participation and outdoor analysis work [10]. Mutual cooperation is the main theme in student-centred approach; facilitator gives them chance to improve their presentation and communication skills [11]. By presenting and answering questions, students learn how to counteract to a sudden situation and the students learn to thin out of the box [2]. According to [9], unlike teacher-centred approach, the teacher gives a student full autonomy to explore the things and play his part passively by reviewing the progress and by facilitating them to solve their queries in student-centred approach.

3.4 Significance of Social Media

Recent times have shown that use of social media is rapidly increasing [2]. Facebook and YouTube are the two most common and widely used social media [5]. However, [4] asserted that Twitter, Whatsapp, and Google are also used by students. Selwyn further mentioned that people use these media for sharing information, videos, pictures, and for chatting that is

why these are referred to as social because they aid in real-time communication with peers and acquaintances as well [13]. Moreover, Saw, Abbott, Donaghey, and McDonald suggested that these media also helps in decision making by enabling students and researchers to do exploratory studies on a specific topic [12].

The importance of social media can be seen from the frequencies of social media applications as used by users and the method of use of different medium used by the public (see figure) are flexible, faster, convenient and user-friendly [2]. Most of them are free and some of them require little investment as compare to conventional means of communication, networking, and studies. Moreover, Chu and Du contended that the flexibility of data sharing among students of remote areas in real-time made social media more powerful [4].

Figure 1: Frequencies of different social media applications - Source:(<http://epceurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/epc-trends-social-media.pdf>)

As shown in figure 2, YouTube and Facebook are most common widely used social Media [13]. Following this the significance of social media is obvious; the primary use of social media is for learning purposes [11]. It was observed that most of

the students in the universities are using social media platforms for learning and education purposes as it is giving them a comprehensive pool of information and data sharing. The observation conducted as to cater the behaviour of students towards awareness and usefulness of social media also enlightens the fact that the advancement in mobile phone technology has further aided in their education. Students have installed mobile applications of social media platform on their mobile phone because it is easy to carry here and there, and they can use it whenever they want [11]. They do not have to carry tablets and laptops along with them anymore.

Likewise, an online survey of 120 students was carried out by a researcher Guy about the knowledge of a respective social medium and results were collected about sixteen social media i.e. Stumble Upon, Wiki, LinkedIn, Blogs, Netlog, Jaiku, Twitter, YouTube, Podcasts, Virtual Worlds, Bulletin Board, RSS, Digg, Delicious, Facebook, and Plurk [6]. The results showed that 70%-85% students had a sound knowledge of Facebook, YouTube, and Wiki; about 40%- 57% students knew about Blogs, Podcasts, LinkedIn, and Forums; 60% students were familiar with Twitter; and 38%- 25% students had been using Virtual World and RSS while; other social media are still unfamiliar to students.

3.5 Social Media in Higher Studies

Social media has a potential in the field of education and learning. Most common media used in this field are YouTube, blogs, and wiki [7]. The wider scope of YouTube is due to the video that can be uploaded and downloaded by students on any area of discussion [2]. Besides, these media comes as second in line for discussions, assignments and group meeting [3]. Chinese students mostly use qq.com as a means of gathering information on different topics that aid in their education [11]. When students were interviewed; 26% of the students said that social networking platform is used for entertainment and learning, 15% said that they use social media for entertainment purpose while 25% came up with the answer that they are using social networking website for socialising with others and the remaining 33% said that they use social networking platform for the purpose of studies.

Figure 2: Use of social media

According to Pea et al. the rewards and advantages that can be derived by the use of social media are countless, however; to name a few; the educators can benefit through program exchanges, they can create or search for relief funds, and they can publish their own studies or the ones conducted by their students [10]. Moreover, Bogdanov, Limpens, Li, Helou, Salzmann and Gillet asserted that educators who use a large database can generate course plans and other activities more effectively [3]. The positive outcomes of social media platform in higher education comprise of total freedom from time constraints. There is visible improvement in quality and efficiency of learning because of computer use [7].

3.6 Hindrances in Education for Chinese students

The Chinese way of teaching primarily depends upon cramming and requires that students memorise a large sum of data. They focus on their native language that is why Chinese Students face difficulty in communicating in English [14]. Mustonen mentioned that China has its own counterparts for social media and they ban the foreign social media to promote their native media is a beneficial way of promoting own identity [9]. However, Li and Chin highlighted that it impedes the flow of foreign information. Li and Chen cited that Youku is used against YouTube, Twitter is replaced by Sina Weibo, and Netease is a substitute of Google's blog posts [8].

Social Platforms in the West	Social Platforms in China
YouTube	Youku
Facebook	Renren.com
Twitter	Sina Weibo, Tencent Weibo
Wikipedia	Baiduzhidao

Blogspot, WordPress	Sina Tencent, Netease
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Table 1: Social Platforms in China

Students from all over the world who are studying abroad find it very challenging to adapt themselves to a culture where educational practices are wholly different from their own country, where language is also an added barrier and difference of norms affects them immensely [10]. They try to draw out on individual, communal, institutional and technological means to counter these issues [11]. Specifically citing the case of Chinese students who have shifted to other countries for study purposes it is generally assumed that the challenges faced by them in terms of differences are usually low analytical thinking ability, little classroom partaking, or insufficient English adeptness [1]. However, it is important to point out that according to Pea et al. these assumptions are made without sufficiently relating to the cultural rationale for those challenges, and their response has not been examined sufficiently [10]. Qiu, Lin and Leung mentioned that research studies have ignored their backgrounds and their cultural differences [11]. According to Ali et al., Chinese students who are in their first academic year of education had never left their country prior to joining foreign institutions [1]. Furthermore, Bogdanov et al. suggested that the challenges that were identified were common and they had left a great impact on them [3]. Those challenges were writing, thinking and speaking [10]. To counter this problem in the interview half of the participants found writing a very tough task. The main reason for stating this is their unfamiliarity with the use of language. Another major stress factor that has been figured out that they had to struggle with an anticipation that was different from what they had experienced in China. The students found international writing tasks very lengthy and the style adopted was challenging for them rather than descriptive [9].

Contrastingly, [6], pointed out the main difference was eastern and western thinking, the eastern thinking was assumed to be intuitive and contextual whereas, the western thinking was considered logical and analytical. The thinking challenge was difficult because all along they had learned memorisation over analysis and found themselves totally ill at ease with regards to analytical thinking [3]. While Hrastinski and Aghae documented that most common

hindrance that Chinese students are facing in education is speaking. At the very onset of their studies, these students need time to collect and translate their thoughts into English before they speak, and they found it extremely difficult to partake in the class discussions because they face difficulty with the quick utterance which created problems for them [7]. Ali, Yaacob, Endut, and Langove highlighted that reading is more important than speaking and if speaking proficiency of those student improves they would be able to speak proficiently as well [1]. While Guy asserted that listening is more important than speaking as to process the information [6]. If student process the information only then they can be able to retain and synthesise it in speaking and reading.

3.7 Improvements in Means of Education

The participants of the interview who were in the age group between 15-25 years use social media more than other age groups. As this age reveals that they are the students who are using social media in a larger percentage, therefore, there is a room for improvement in the educational standards used [13]. However, Saw et al. argued that the people with age group 15-25 years old use social media for entertainment purposes [12]. With the use of Social media collaborative and reflective learning can be improved in the distant learning method [3]. Students were enquired about the use of social media for the improvement in learning. The data showed that 23% did not agree with the perception that social media aids in education, however, 62% of them were plainly agreed with the statement. While; 15% were not sure whether the use of social media aids in education or not.

Figure 3: Social media enhance learning

Guy mentioned that mobile technology is useful for improving language skills of Chinese students. They can use translator and online dictionary to learn English [6]. Mobile can be used to download social networking applications like Twitter and YouTube or it can be used to install games which are designed especially for the learning purposes [8]. These games enable users to improve their listening and speaking through solving a puzzle or exploring a treasure. Zaidieh asserted that the approach that has to be adopted for the students is to motivate them intrinsically otherwise a language barrier can create the demotivating factor for the students [14]. A research documented by Li and Chin, many educational institutions in China are encouraging lessons on the mobile phone because about 900 million students are mobile phone users and it is an easy way to deliver learning activities through social media applications installed on mobile phones [8].

3.8 Social Media Aids in Learning of Chinese Students

Ever since Social media has entered our lives there has been a remarkable change in the way things are dealt with. Unparalleled transformations have taken place in the variety and layout of communiqué [6]. These technological advancements have a step-by-step substituted face to face meetings with virtual ones through technological devices, and it is because of these changes that social media is at the centre stage of all communication modes nowadays [3]. Over the past few years, swift and significant changes have taken place and the global development of social media has gained incredible popularity [5].

As Pea et al. mentioned, China published a mobile newspaper application “Daily China” in English-Chinese language in 2008 to facilitate Chinese students by giving news two times a day [10]. This can further be extended to daily mobile lessons. A daily alert can be sent to the mobile phone of the subscriber (student) before broadcasting so that he might not miss any lecture. Application of dictionary has embedded a word of the day feature which can further be extended to the phrase of the day and a daily pop-up message to the user can be added in the application [14].

Moreover, the largest social forum used by Chinese students is www.qq.com; it allows users to visit the

website in their native language and in the English language as well [9]. However, Zaidieh stated that due to the medium of education and social networking website Chinese, students prefer to use it in the Chinese language [14]. He further suggested that it should be in only English language to improve their proficiency. However, Ali et al. contend that due to lower proficiency in English language Chinese student will find it uninteresting to visit the page because they will find difficulty in reading [1]. The option of their native language is also present there they can compare the words of Chinese language into the English language. This will increase their expertise over English language and helpful in overcoming language barriers. Chinese native can also visit the page in his native language if he is finding difficulty in visiting the page in English. This phenomenon will enhance their knowledge base for the discussion on the specific page and for the understanding of a widely used language around the world [4]. Audio blogs can be used to examine the oral capacity of these students.

Twitter is a good way of interaction among students in a targeted culture as specified by the Chinese students [8]. Through interaction with the students of the targeted culture, the knowledge sharing and collaborative learning have been improved. Target culture learning sometimes is not possible on the geographical basis but it is possible on the social media platforms which ease distant learning. Teachers usually add grammar correction feature in tweets which sometimes feel irritating and time-consuming in manual checking [2].

Furthermore, [14] has established this fact that the use of social media has remarkably improved communication skills and participative activities have definitely increased along with social commitment. It has positively affected the education based on collaborative methods. Social media is an inexpensive way of attaining knowledge and help without extensive support from educational institutions at higher levels, which also means that they can be effectively incorporated into the learning processes. It seems that the use of social media has become highly prevalent globally [11]. Above all, social media has given the ability to students to express freely and receive information at any time and share according to their own free will. Chu and Du mentioned that social media has some off-putting factors, for instance, confidentiality, mishandling of

information, and social network reliance. Nevertheless, Qiu et al. argued that the benefits of social media surpass the drawbacks, and if used advantageously it can be immensely helpful in the field of education [11].

4. CONCLUSIONS

The growing use of social media among students is a testimony that it can aid in learning and education of the students. The connectivity of international students provides a scope for Chinese students to participate in the open forum discussion with them. This relationship building provides them with the analysis of differences in the education at home and abroad. Social media in higher studies give Chinese students the advantage of personalised learning ability and get instant feedback. It can be given the credit for bringing out the learning towards voluntary behaviour amongst students in order to improve their research knowledge and skills. It can become more powerful with the collaboration of e-libraries with universities. Students are facing an issue of authenticity of data but with the incorporation of e-libraries, this issue can be mitigated. In addition to this, if Chinese students have access to the foreign media along with their local media the information can be gathered at a broader platform and they can also get responses and feedback from other international students. Through this, they can develop their writing intellectual skills. This article will contribute in providing further research of the growing use of social media and its impact on studies; specifically for the study of Chinese students who are backed by the traditional ways of learning and linguistic barriers.

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6. APPENDIX

6.1 Interview Questionnaire

Question No 1: Does the use of social media supports learning and academic performance?

Question No 2: Does social media causes distraction and divert the mind from studies or academic achievement when studying on social networking websites?

Question No 3: What are the factors that motivate the use of social media platform?

Question No 4: What are the primary media which you use most?

Question No 5: Should more colleges offer online educational resources to their students in place of overpriced books?

Question No 6: Do you agree that students have found the relationship between academic performance and use of social media platforms?

Question No 7: In your opinion, is social media successful in alleviating barriers to education which Chinese students are facing in the home country and in the host country?

Question No 8: Is it possible to excel in higher studies without the use of social media?

Question No 9: Do you think social media of China is creating hindrances in the inflow of foreign information by replacing foreign social media?

Question No 10: Do you think demographic factors influence the level of education?